

Five years of Open Search Initiative – where do we stand?

S. Voigt, C. Plote, C. Geminn and F. Hauser, Open Search Foundation, Starnberg, Germany

Abstract

The Open Search Initiative advocates for an independent, free and self-determined access to information on the internet. Its goal is a web search that is not profit-driven but based upon ethical values and fundamental rights - a web search ecosystem that offers manifold choices, including public as well as commercially driven services. In the year 2022 the Open Search Initiative is in its fifth year of existence and many scientific organisations, universities, computing centres, dedicated individuals, administrative bodies, foundations, NGOs, start-ups and companies are cooperating therein and are developing concepts, components, and general rules for the envisaged open search ecosystem. Their common driver is not profit, however, the goal of an internet search that benefits everyone.

The basic idea of the initiative is to build the web search ecosystem based on open and auditable source code; distributed crawling, indexing and hosting across many different computing centres and language spaces; as well as on public moderation and democratic oversight of the infrastructure. It is the aim to make web search a common good that is implemented and maintained by public and partially maybe also private actors, as it is the case with other relevant infrastructure such as roads, water supply or electricity. It will allow the building of a diversity of search frontends and will furthermore enable establishing many other open web analysis services, both, public/free of charge or commercially driven.

During the first years, the Open Search Initiatives focussed on spreading and jointly sharpening the concepts, as well as on building an interdisciplinary network of supporters, addressing the many different technical, organisational, legal, ethical and societal aspects of cooperative and open web search. After a first stakeholder workshop in 2017 and establishing the Open Search Foundation as non-profit organisation in 2018, a growing community built up during the past five years. Currently more than 120 individuals from more than 50 organisations, from 12, mainly European, countries are actively contributing to it. With several specialist groups cooperating in different disciplines and a number of events being organised for fundraising, community building, awareness raising and scientific exchange. The initiative has developed an sound momentum momentum already and the central event is the yearly International Open Search Symposium, with the first #ossym held in 2019 at Leibniz Supercomputing Center and in subsequent years at CERN.

It is clear, that web search is more than a technological challenge. Many aspects play a role, such as legal, ethical, economic, and educational disciplines. In order to address this diversity, six specialist working groups were establishing helping to structure the work, better coordinate the developments and improve the

communication: Awareness, Application, Economy, Ethics, Legal and Tech.

A key activity is raising awareness for the open search idea with organisations, public bodies, politics as well as the general public. To this end, the initiative could already successfully inspire the European Commission to start supporting research on open search and it raised interest of, and is in dialogue with, members of the European and German parliament, it gained support by several federal and 'Länder' Ministries in Germany and liaised with many NGOs, start-ups, universities, foundations etc. Further more, several partner organisations established internal open search related projects and activities, to strengthen and coordinate their contribution (e.g. DLR, LRZ, CERN and several universities). Furthermore, teams of the the community could raise dedicated project support and funds from public donors and foundations, e.g. European Commission, Stiftung Mercator, BMW-Foundation and NLNet. These range from a few ten-thousand Euros for individual projects to several million Euro of research funds for the OpenWebSearch.EU EC Horizon Europe project.

Where do we stand with the Open Search Initiative? Reflecting the developments and the achievements described above, the Open Search Initiative can be considered as having left its initial phase. A substantial group of relevant organisations, science centres, universities, computing centres and concerned individuals are engaging and is cooperating. Awareness and concern about single platforms controlling access to information on the Internet is significantly raising. Through the work of different specialist groups within the initiative, key aspects and development tasks for the envisaged open web search ecosystem could already be identified and are being currently further developed.

Next important steps: With the basic technical, organisational and societal dimensions of an open search ecosystem being identified, it will be important during this next phase of the initiative to connect these different dimensions through: a) Intensifying the dialogue between the involved disciplines, b) Elaborating first concrete principles, rules of engagement and interfaces for operating the open search ecosystem, technically and organisationally and c) Implementing and operating a first substantial and lasting prototype, to demonstrate the full potential of open web search. In parallel to this, it will be important to bring open web search on the political agenda at European level as well as in Member States, to ensure concrete commitments in terms of funding and legislative support. Beyond this, it will important in the coming phase to develop the financing and operating models, as well as the governance framework for an open and cooperative web search infrastructure in Europe. It will be important to develop the technical, organisational, societal, financial and legislative aspects of this open

search ecosystem in parallel and with close linkages and exchange. By doing so, it will be possible to implement and scale the open search idea at the necessary pace and to bring it to routine operation across Europe and for

different language spaces and top-level domains. All this can only be achieved if a cooperative and team-play approach can be maintained. Together, for a better net.